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Textile Engineering College, Zorargonj, Chattogram.

**B.Sc. in Textile Engineering
Project (Thesis) on**

**Effectiveness of bio-scouring over conventional scouring
on cotton knitted fabric.**

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**This report presented in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of
Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.**

OCTOBER, 2019

DECLARATION

We hereby declare that, this project has been done by us under the supervision of **Tariqul Islam, Lecturer (Technical), and Department of Wet Processing Engineering**, Textile Engineering College, Zorargonj, Chattogram. We also declare that neither this project nor any part of this project has been submitted elsewhere for award of any degree.

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To

Tariqul Islam

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Subject: Submission of Project Report

Dear Sir,

We are very pleased to submit our project report title as “Effectiveness of bio- scouring over conventional scouring on cotton knitted fabric”, that was required for graduation on B.Sc. in Textile Engineering from Textile Engineering College, Zorargonj, Chattogram.

In presenting this report, we have tried our level best to include all the relevant information and the explanation, to make the report informative and comprehensive.

May we therefore pray and hope that you would like to be kind enough to grand our submission and oblige thereby.

Sincerely on behalf of your students

Pranay Dutta

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First and foremost, praises and thanks to God, the Almighty, for His showers of blessings throughout our project work to complete the project successfully.

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Abstract

The introduction of enzymes in the treatment of textiles has made a significant contribution to the textile sector. The traditional pretreatment scouring process has many drawbacks, conciliated by handling with enzymes. Since most factories still use traditional pretreatment to obviate natural impurities from cotton knit fabric, they experience a lot of water, electricity, steam, and time consumption, and more significant fiber loss. Also, the conventional pretreatment method leads to significant amount of wastewater that has a detrimental impact on the environment. If we use enzyme rather than chemicals used in conventional processing, the fiber damage will be less, cost will come down, the processes will be eco-friendly, and so do the water released by then and most importantly the effect will be better in this case. In other words, we will get a better quality product with eco-friendly process if we use enzyme instead of conventional chemicals. Hence, the main focus of the paper is to investigate whether there is the usability and replace ability of the enzyme scouring process over the caustic soda scouring process on cotton knit fabric or not. In this research, cotton knit fabrics was scoured by SCOUR-ZYME (bio-scouring enzyme) and caustic soda. Physicochemical parameters of the wastewater derived from caustic scouring and enzymatic scouring had been examined. Some selected physical characteristics including absorbency test, percentage of weight loss, whiteness index, moisture regain, moisture content, bursting strength, color fastness to wash, rubbing and perspiration, were also analyzed for scoured and dyed materials. As a result, bio-scouring method improved the absorption of the material without any substantial loss of strength and helped to properly dye and finish the cloth. Substantial lower consumption of electricity, water, streams, chemicals, and time and, consequently, cost, environmental pressures were reduced in the enzyme method. Physicochemical parameters test results indicated more significant ecological improvement than the traditional approach for using enzymes. What is more, the physical characteristics also demonstrated better outcomes in the use of enzymatic scouring method except some cases. Therefore, we cannot ensure it as an only substitute because it does not give desired result in some cases. Although both have some restriction in the textile sector, they can be properly utilized by evaluating their respective merits and drawbacks. Thus, this work provided a set of experimental results, discussion and comparison between the two methods.

Chapter One

Introduction

One of the biggest industries in the world is the textile industry. The textile industry creates job opportunities which are without a higher level of knowledge and which are a vital factor in providing jobs in poverty-stricken countries such as Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Vietnam, and thus playing a crucial role in the growth of their GDP [1]. This industry serves several sectors with as varied operational activities as its products.

Greige cotton fibers made up approximately 95% pure cellulose, balanced by non-cellulosic impurities of protein, oil, wax, pectin, carbohydrates, and inorganic materials [2-3]. For all subsequent finishing processes, namely dyeing, printing, and finishing, various treatments must be performed to remove natural non-cellulosic materials during the preparation of cellulosic materials [4]. Pretreatment of textile materials is essential; without pretreatment, the cotton coloring is almost impossible to achieve the desired result [5]. During all phases of processing fibers, fabrics and garments, the textile industry produces a wide range of contaminants that has a detrimental effect on the environment.

In the dispensation of cotton and cotton mixed content, scouring is an essential pretreatment process. The primary aim of the scouring is to obviate non-cellulosic cotton fibre additives and make the fiber absorbent. The traditional scouring process on cotton knitted fabric is carried out with temperatures of 95°C with the sodium hydroxide in a higher alkaline medium [6-9]. Caustic scouring includes many synthetic chemical compounds that are poisonous and hazardous to human skin and the environment.

In conventional scouring method, several toxic chemical compounds are used, which increases the BOD, COD and TDS amount in the wastewater and raise the undesirable environmental pressure. It generates a. over half the total BOD b. just less than half of COD and c. one-tenth of the overall level of pollution produced throughout the production process [10-11].

Since caustic soda works on swelling method and targets the secondary cell wall of cotton, which is almost pure cellulose; as a result, caustic soda destroys the cotton fibers and its strength during the conventional scouring processes. Besides, it encourages the dye molecules

not to be fixed on the fiber's surface according to our needs, and it accounts for a substantial quantity of dye loss. In reality, weight loss is roughly more than a tenth, potentially resulting in unnecessary weight loss.

Caustic scouring is conducted at 95 °C. In order to maintain this temperature, a lot more energy is needed in which field we are combating and more time is required, and it decreases production efficiency. Furthermore, the health of employees is severely impaired by the processing of these harmful chemicals in conventional caustic soda scouring.

In the textile industry, the main environmental issue concerns the volume of water and the chemical load it bears. The dyeing sector in textile is extremely water-intensive. Water is used during the entire production process to clean the raw material and for many different steps. It was found that nearly two-fifths of water is used during the bleaching process, and a fifth of water is used in dyeing. Also, less than a tenth of water is used in the printing process, while nearly a fifth of water is being used in printing, and only a quarter of water is used in other purposes [12-13]. The production of 1 kilogram of textile goods involves around 200 liters of water [14]. The caustic soda scouring consists of a number of overflows to subdue the scouring baths for subsequent operations that raise the need for water volume and high pH levels. It is a very concerning matter, as we only use a large volume of water, such as about 45,000 liters of water is used per 1000 kilograms of products for the scouring process [15]. Conventional caustic scouring requires a considerable amount of expense in the ETP to refine the wastewater, which is the principal cause of industries not getting the efficient management of wastes. Moreover, in these processes, we can see that large quantities of contaminated water are released. The truth is that the water released after textile processing is well above the norms and comprises a significant quantity of harsh chemical substances that are hazardous to the environment.

There are reports that over 10,000 diverse colorants are industrially used. Each year, more than 7 tons of synthetic dyes are manufactured worldwide [16-17]. In Bangladesh, this sector is experiencing a great deal of decrrial over the past few years for rising pollution because most dyeing industries have been established on the river in Bangladesh, leading to water environmental degradation. It is predicted that traditional dyeing activities in 2021 generate approximately 348 million cubic meters of wastewater [18].

Generally, dyes and pigments are being widely used in the dyeing industry. As a lot of chemical compounds are added in the dyeing process, around a fifth of the dyes due in the dye bath and are released along with other residual chemical substances as exhausted dye bath residue. The exhausted dye bath residues also consist of large amounts of colored content and add color to the receiving water bodies. Their release into rivers is detrimental to aquatic life due to the high concentrations of organic matter in wastewater and greater durability of modern synthetic dyes. As some of the dyes are made up of complex molecular forms, this helps them remain more stable and unlikely to decompose [19-26].

The greatest obstacle for the clothing industry today is improving manufacturing methods so that they are environmentally sustainable at a reasonable cost, utilizing safer dyes and chemical compounds and cutting the amount of effluent treatment cost. It has become a crucial requirement for the factory managers to figure out a substitute for the conventional caustic soda scouring process for some of its inevitable drawbacks.

On the contrary, the introduction of enzymes in the treatment of textiles has made a significant contribution to the textile sector. This is because with the increasingly important requirement for textile industries to reduce pollution in textile production, the use of enzymes in the chemical processing of fibers, and textiles is rapidly gaining wider recognition because of their non-toxic and eco-friendly characteristics. Furthermore, enzymes were discovered in the second half of the nineteenth century, and since are routinely used in many environmentally friendly and economic industrial sectors. There is increasing demand to replace some traditional chemical processes with biotechnological processes involving microorganisms and enzymes such as pectinases, xylanases, cellulases, laccases and ligninases [27-28]. These enzymes can be used efficiently for scouring instead of traditional caustic soda scouring. This enables the development of eco-friendly fiber processing techniques and applications to enhance the end product attribute. The critical factor behind the use of enzymes in the finishing of textile products is the use of energy resources and the greater understanding of environmental issues relating to the use and discharge of hazardous substances into low-lying lands, rivers, and other water bodies during the chemical treatment of textiles. Bio-scouring enables an effective scouring of the fabric without adversely impacting the fabric or our surroundings [29].

To save the earth's health is a main concern in our society at the moment. In view of the possibility of industrial waste streams, governments and communities are getting aware of environmental-related issues. Garment industries are confronting several difficulties from ecological issues and environmental regulation, incorporating higher water prices, ETP and disposal prices, more astringent legislations, and the implementation of ISO 14001, in particular [30]. Dyeing plants contaminate the water bodies will confront the danger of closing down, which has just begun in Bangladesh.

In Bangladesh, cotton fibers are being dyed with traditional reactive dyes and caustic soda scouring process is being widely used compared to enzymatic scouring process because of the accessibility of resources. That is why nobody is worrying about the effect on the ecosystem.

To minimize the above-mentioned causes of environmental pollution of our country as well as the whole world this research is a little approach. This paper contains not only the investigation of the environmental impact of bio-scouring on cotton knit fabric processing, but also the investigation of the environmental impact of caustic soda scouring. Comparative research was carried out on specific selected physical characteristics of both types of finished products.

1.1 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of our work is to investigate whether there is the usability and replace ability of the enzyme scouring process over the caustic soda scouring process on cotton knit fabric or not, as well as to find out the effectiveness of bio-scouring over conventional scouring on cotton knitted fabric as for time, cost and energy.

1.2 Experimental Design

The experimental design will be shown in the following flowchart(Figure 1).

Figure 1: Flowchart demonstration of experimental designing.

Chapter Two

Literature Review

Raw fibers, yarns or fabrics have various kinds of impurities like motes, seed coat fragments, pesticides, dirt, chemical residues, metallic salts of various kinds, and immature fibers. External impurities are removed in the blow room processing while internal impurities of cotton fibers removed by scouring processes. Cotton fiber is constituted with different layers in its body. Different constituent of cotton fibers are cellulose (90%-94%), waxes (0.6%-1.3%), pectic substances (0.9%-1.2%), protein (0.6%-1.3%), organic acids (up to 0.8%) and others (1.2%) [31-32].

Thus, raw cotton fibers have to go through several chemical processes to obtain properties suitable for use. With scouring, non-cellulose substances (wax, pectin, proteins, and hemicelluloses) that surround the fiber cellulose core are removed, and as a result, fibers become hydrophilic and suitable for bleaching, dyeing and other processing.

By removing pectin, it is easier to remove all others uncellulosic substances. For this purpose, caustic soda (NaOH) treatment is used in conventional scouring, whereas enzyme treatment is applied in bio-scouring process. The processes of bio-scouring that are in use today are based on the decomposition of pectin by the enzymes called pectinases.

Enzymes are biological catalysts that accelerate the rate of chemical reactions [33]. All enzymes are made of protein and they each have a very specific 3 dimensional shape. The shape is different for each enzyme and each enzyme only works on one substance or type of chemical reaction i.e. amylase speeds up the breakdown of starch into the sugar maltose. Catalyses speed up the breakdown of hydrogen peroxide. The reason for this is that the substrate fits into a special region of the enzyme called the active site. When in the active site the enzyme can catalyze the reaction. The active site is a special shape and will therefore only allow molecules of a certain shape inside. The reaction happens with lower activation energy which is reached by forming an intermediate enzyme – substrate. Later the substrate molecule is converted into the product and the enzyme itself is regenerated.

Enzymes can work at atmospheric pressure and in mild conditions with respect to temperature and acidity (pH). Most enzymes function optimally at a temperature of 30°C-70°C and at pH values, which are near the neutral point (pH 7). Enzyme processes are potentially energy saving and save investing in special equipment resistant to heat, pressure or corrosion. Because of their efficiency, specific action, the mild conditions in which they work and their high biodegradability, enzymes are very well suited for a wide range of industrial applications. For this reasons, enzymes are used in the textile industry as they accelerate reactions, act only on specific substrates, operate under mild conditions, are safe and easy to control, can replace harsh chemicals and are biodegradable. That is why celluloses, pectinases, hemicelluloses, lipases and catalyses are being used in different cotton pre-treatment and finishing processes [33].

Since enzymes are one of the most blessed introductions in textile wet processing pretreatments, enzymes can be effectively used for scouring in textile wet processing. The process is effective enough to crack the waxy film of cotton surface that is sufficient to increase the wetting power of the cloth [34]. The end result is better than the conventional scouring. This can be proved from the increase in scouring effect, dye-ability and color fastness properties of the fabric. Also, enzymatic process involves a few numbers of chemicals. This also solves the problem of toxic water in processing bath; hence, the liquor released after treatment is eco-friendly. Bio-scouring waste water contains 40%-50% less COD and 60% less TDS as compared to conventional scouring waste water [10]. In addition, lower amount of heat reduces the energy and the reduced number of chemicals reduces the cost of the process. The fabrics treated with harsh chemicals are also unsafe for human health because it may affect on human skin, but bio-scoured fabrics are completely safe. Therefore, a better quality eco-friendly economic product is the possible outcome if we replace the conventional chemical scouring process with enzyme.

Chapter Three

Materials and Methods

3.1 Raw Materials

The utilized materials are-

Types of fabrics: 100% S/J (single jersey) Cotton

Count: 30^s

GSM: 160

3.2 Chemicals

The Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd supplied SCOUR-ZYME (a commercial grade enzyme) for the enzymatic scouring process. Sodium hydroxide and soda ash were used for the caustic scouring process. Chemical auxiliaries, such as SHUNTEX XPA (sequestering agent), PERSOCLAN STN (wetting agent), FEROL-ZOM (detergent), RUBINE OS (anti creasing agent), ANTIFOAMING JET (anti-foaming agent), and citric acid were provided by Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd.

3.3 Conventional Method of Scouring

1 gram per litre of caustic soda and 2 gram per litre of Na₂CO₃ is used for traditional caustic scouring. Since wet processing water can have hard water compounds, i.e. 30 ppm hardness was discovered; for this reason, 0.20 gram per litre SHUNTEX XPA was used. In addition, the scouring of caustic soda was performed with a 1:8 ratio of liquor, 1 gram per litre of PERSOCLAN STN, 2 gram per litre of FEROL-ZOM, 1 gram per litre of RUBINE STN, 1.50 gram per litre citric acid and 0.05 gram per litre of ANTIFOAMING JET at 95°C for the period of one hour.

3.4 Method of Bio-Scouring

0.80% of SCOUR-ZYME has been used for enzymatic scouring. Citric acid was used for the enzyme so that enzyme can work at a suitable pH. The pH of the bathtub was 6.5. Furthermore, 1 gram per litre of PERSOCLAN STN, 0.05 gram per litre of ANTIFOAMING JET, 1 gram per litre of FEROL-ZOM, and 1:8 of liquor ratio have been used at 55 ° C for a half-hour. The following demonstrates a process graph for enzymatic scouring.

Figure 2: Pictorial Illustration of the Caustic Scouring Curve.

Figure 3: Pictorial Illustration of the Bio-Scouring Curve.

3.5 Assessment of Absorbency Test

3.5.1 Drop Test

Water is taken in the pipette, and the water drops are fall on the scoured cloth and observe the absorption of the water droplet.

3.5.2 Spot Test

In pipette, a 1% solution of reactive blue dye is taken and places the drops of solution in different parts of the fabric. Next, notice the shape of the absorption place of the fabric.

3.5.3 Wicking test

During a glass beaker, the cotton content strip (18 cm × 5 cm) was suspended higher than the H₂O line; the end of such a horizontal plane contacts the surface of the water. Capillary force discovered natural wicking. The peaks of the fluid height range were recorded for 5, 10, and 15 minutes.

3.5.4 Sinking test

Absorption can be used in a number of ways, the most common being the sinking time check. Test specimens measuring 1 cm × 1 cm were cut randomly and mounted on the surface of the water. The sample was slowly wetted, and the air trapped was extracted. It was noted that the time is taken for the sample to go within the water from the floating state and sunk in absolutely.

3.6 Percentage of Loss of Weight

The weight loss of the materials was determined by distinguishing between the pre-and post-treatment. Once the treatment was completed, the material was dried and weighed.

$$\text{Wt. \%} = \frac{A - B}{A} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where, A and B is the weights of fabrics before and after scouring.

3.7 Assessment of Whiteness Index

The whiteness index of the scoured and bleached specimens was analyzed by the reflectance value of the spectrophotometer (Data color 650TM).

3.8 Assessment of Moisture Regain and Moisture Content Test

The quantity of water present in a textile sample shall be determined either by its regain or by its moisture content. Method ASTM D2495-07 is used to perform the test. The specimens were taken and weighed before being oven-dried at 105 °C until a constant weight is maintained. The difference between the initial pre-drying mass and the oven-drying mass is measured as a percentage.

$$\text{Moisture Regain, } R = \frac{W}{D} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Moisture Content, } C = \frac{100R}{R+100} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where, D is the oven dry wt. of the materials and W is the wt. of water in the fabrics.

3.9 Assessment of Bursting Strength Test

The pneumatic method (ISO 13938-2: 1999) was used to assess the samples' bursting strength.

3.10 Assessment of Color Fastness to Rubbing

ISO 105-X12: 1993 method is used to conduct the fabric test. Using crock meter, 20cm×5cm of sample size, 5cm×5cm of bleached fabric, and given rotation of 10 cycles for 10 seconds to carry out the test.

3.11 Assessment of Color Fastness to Washing

ISO 105-C06 B2S procedure is used to conduct the fabric test. 1g/L of $\text{BNaO}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 4g/L of ECE phosphate detergent were used. Also, 10cm × 4cm of sample size, 10cm × 4cm of multi-fibers size, and 25 number of steel ball were used at 50°C for 30 minutes to perform the test.

3.12 Assessment of Color Fastness to Perspiration

ISO 105-E04:2013 procedure is used to conduct the fabric test. 0.5g/L of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}_2 \cdot \text{HCl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.2g/L of Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate dihydrate, 5g/L of NaCl were used for the acidic solution. Moreover, 10cm × 4cm of sample size and 10cm × 4cm of multi-fibers size were used at 37°C for 4 hours to conduct the test. 5.5 of the pH value were maintained in this test.

Furthermore, 0.5g/L of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}_2 \cdot \text{HCl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.5g/L of disodium hydrogen phosphate dihydrate, 5g/L of NaCl were used for the alkaline solution. In addition, 10cm × 4cm of sample size and 10cm × 4cm of multi-fibers size were used at 37°C for 4 hours to operate the test. 8.0 of the pH value were maintained in this test.

3.13 Physicochemical Parameters Test

The effluents were collected, and numerous physicochemical parameters of the effluents test were carried out after all the pre-treatment processes of both samples.

3.13.1 Biochemical Oxygen Demand

The levels of oxygen are needed for the oxidative activity of organic compounds in water is called Biochemical Oxygen Demand. BOD is not only used for water quality control and assessment, but it is also used in ecology and environmental sciences. This test is carried out in the following standard procedure (*Method APHA 5210B*): the known sample volume has its initial dissolved oxygen content registered. After five days of incubation at 20°C, the sample is

obviated from the incubator, and the final content of the dissolved oxygen is obviated. The value of BOD is determined based on the degradation and the amount of the sample used. Determine the BOD value according to the following formula:

$$\text{Blank correction} = \text{Burette Reading for blank at } DO_i - \text{B.R. for blank at } DO_f \quad (4)$$

$$\text{BOD} = [(\text{Burette Reading for sample at } DO_i - DO_f) - \text{blank correction}] \times \text{dilution factor} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Dilution factor} = \frac{\text{volume of bottle (300 mL)}}{\text{sample volume}} \quad (6)$$

Where DO_i = initial Dissolved Oxygen, and DO_f = day five after incubation.

3.13.2 Chemical Oxygen Demand

The levels of oxygen are needed to oxidize the organic and inorganic matters present in water called COD. This test is carried out in the following procedure (*Method APHA 5220B*): Organic and oxidizing inorganic compounds in the sample are oxidized by $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in a 50 % H_2SO_4 solution at its boiling point. Ag_2SO_4 is used as a catalyst, and $HgSO_4$ is used to eliminate the effects of chloride. Using standard $Fe (NH_4)_2(SO_4)_2$ that uses the $C_{36}H_{24}FeN_6^{+2}$ as an indicator, the excessive quantity of $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ is titrated. Determine the COD value according to the following formula:

$$\text{COD} = \frac{(V_1 - V_2) \times M \times 8000}{\text{mL of sample taken}} \quad (7)$$

Where V_1 = FAS [Ammonium iron(II) sulfate] solution needed for the blank (in mL),
 V_2 = FAS solution needed for the sample (in mL),
 and M = Molarity of FAS solution.

3.13.3 Alkalinity

Alkalinity is measured by volumetric titration at 0.02 N H_2SO_4 and reported as $CaCO_3$ equivalent.

3.13.4 pH and Electrical Conductivity

pH is the calculation of the acidic or basic state of the negative logarithm of the concentration of hydrogen ion in sample water. pH test is carried out using a standard Pinpoint pH meter. A measurement of electrical solution conductivity assesses its ability to conduct electricity. Using a multimeter (Apera Instruments AI316 Premium Series PC 60), conductivity (mS/cm) value was found directly.

3.13.5 Total Solids

Total Solids (TS) refer to the thing remaining as residual after volatilization and drying up at 105°C for a period of 24 hours. Method APHA 2540 B is carried out to determine the TS. Calculate total solids (TS) as follows:

$$\text{Total Solids} = \frac{(W_2 - W_1) \times 1000}{\text{sample volume}} \quad (8)$$

Where, W_2 = weight of filter paper + dried residue, and W_1 = weight of filter paper.

3.13.6 Total Dissolved Solids

TDS are solid particles in water, undergoing via the filter. TDS is resolved by Method APHA 2540 C.

$$\text{Hence, TDS} = \text{TS} - \text{TSS} \quad (9)$$

3.13.7 Dissolved Oxygen

DO is that the levels of oxygen are dissolved in water, necessary for safe streams and rivers. The value of Dissolved Oxygen may be an indication of how dirty water is and how well water can sustain aquatic plant and animal life. The most common method for the measurement of Dissolved Oxygen is the dissolved oxygen meter and sensor (Model: JPB-70A).

3.13.8 Total Suspended Solids

TSS are solid particles in water, be contained by a filter. According to Method APHA 2540 D is carried out the test.

$$\text{TSS} = \frac{(W_4 - W_3) \times 1000}{\text{sample volume}} \quad (10)$$

Where, W_4 = wt. of filter paper + dried residue, and W_3 = wt. of filter paper.

Chapter Four

Results and Discussion

4.1 Weight Loss Result

Table 1: Test Results of Weight Loss (%)

Sample No	Before weight (gm)	After weight (gm)	Weight loss %
Sample-1 (conventional)	10	9.77	2.3
Sample-2 (bio-scouring)	10	9.90	0.96

Figure 4: Comparison between bio-scoured and conventional scoured fabrics in terms of weight loss %

Observation: From the analysis, we can see that the percentage of weight loss is greater in the traditional caustic soda process than in the enzymatic process. This is because partial amount of cellulose is removed with impurities, namely wax, protein, pectin, oil etc. in the traditional process.

4.2 Absorbency Test Result

4.2.1 Wicking Test

Table 2: Test Results of Wicking Test

Sample No	Length Of Immersed Fabric (mm)	Standard Dipped Length (mm)
Sample-1 (conventional)	92	30-50
	95	
	101	
Sample-2 (bio-scouring)	64	
	76	
	96	

Figure 5: Comparison between bio-scoured and conventional scoured in terms of wicking height

Observation: From the above table, the results reveal that enzymatic scoured specimens are in optimal absorbing range compared with traditional caustic soda scoured specimens. This result demonstrates distinct differences between caustic soda scouring and enzymatic scouring.

Serial No	Bio-scouring sample	Conventional scouring sample
1		
2		
3		

Figure 6: Absorbency test of bio and conventional scouring (wicking test) samples

4.2.2 Spot Test

Table 3: Test Results of Spot Test

Bio-scouring Sample	Caustic scouring sample
Good scouring	Uniform scouring

Observation: We can see from the findings that the enzymatic scoured material was quite well scoured than the traditional caustic soda scoured material.

4.2.3 Drop Test

Table 4: Test Results of Drop Test

Sample No	Time (sec)
Sample-1 (conventional)	1.20
	0.69
	0.24
Sample-2 (bio-scouring)	0.24
	0.53
	0.45

Observation: Compared with the traditional caustic soda scoured specimens, the absorbency of enzymatic scoured specimens is quite satisfactory because enzymatic scoured materials take less time to absorb water drops in comparison to traditional caustic soda scoured materials.

4.2.4 Sinking Test

Table 5: Test Results of Sinking Test

Sample No	Time (sec)
Sample-1 (conventional)	2.37
Sample-2 (bio-scouring)	1.82

Observation: The less time is taken by the materials to sink fully into the water, the higher its absorbency. From the analysis, the result reveals that compared with the traditional caustic soda scoured materials, time taken by the enzymatic scoured materials is lower.

4.3 Whiteness Index Result

Table 6: Test Results of Whiteness Index

Sample No	Whiteness Index
Sample-1 (conventional)	36.84
Sample-2 (bio-scouring)	16.05

Observation: The outcome of the study shows that compared to the traditional caustic soda scoured materials, the whiteness value of the enzymatic scoured materials is lower. Its appearance is yellowish because inadequate elimination of seed-coat fragments and mote properly in the scouring phases. These are obviated during the bleaching process, and the whiteness is enhanced by approximately 45.

4.4 Moisture Regain and Moisture Content Test Result

Table 7: Test Results of Moisture Regain and Moisture Content Test

Sample No	Moisture Regain (%)	Moisture Content (%)
Sample-1 (conventional)	6.27	5.90
Sample-2 (bio-scouring)	6.83	6.39

Observation: There are 6.83% of moisture regain for sample no 2 while the figure for sample no 1 stood at only 6.27%. As the percentage of moisture regain depend on effective scouring; as a result, sample no 2 shows higher value compared to sample no 1. Similarly, moisture content for bio-scoured fabric reveals higher value.

4.5 Bursting Strength Test

Table 8: Test Results of Pneumatic Bursting Strength Test

Sample No	Distension (mm)	kPa
Sample-1 (conventional)	15.79	255.15
Sample-2 (bio-scouring)	16.16	282.43
Grey Fabric	16.41	292.54

Observation: The strength of the enzymatic scoured specimen shows greater value than traditional caustic soda scoured specimen. Enzyme scouring allows the elimination of the cuticle portion by partial hydrolysis. This is why, after enzymatic treatment, cotton has an intact structure with a lower strength.

4.6 Rubbing Fastness Test Result

Table 9: Assessment Color Fastness to Rubbing

Sample No	Shade%	Type	Rating Bleached cotton
Sample-1 (bio-scouring fabric)	1.0%	Dry	4/ 5
		Wet	3/4
	2.0%	Dry	4/5
		Wet	4
Sample-2 (conventional scouring)	1.0%	Dry	4/ 5
		Wet	3/4
	2.0%	Dry	4/5
		Wet	3/4

Observation: In comparison to caustic treated fabric with Remazol brand reactive dyed specimens, enzyme-treated fabric with Avitera brand dyed materials deliver greater values for 1% and 2% shades. It can be clarified in this way that Avitera brand dye has more flexibility for connecting to cellulose fibers, which ensures that the properties of color fastness are also greater in rating.

4.7 Color Fastness to Perspiration Result

Table 10: Assessment of Color Fastness to Perspiration

Sample	Shade%	Type	Grey scale Rating
Bio-scoured fabrics	1.0%	Alkali	4
		Acid	4/5
	2.0%	Alkali	4/5
		Acid	4/5
Conventional scoured fabrics	1.0%	Alkali	4
		Acid	4/5
	2.0%	Alkali	4
		Acid	4/5

Observation: This color fastness to perspiration shows the results in terms of color staining. Color fastness to perspiration doesn't show a significant change but the differences are well observable.

4.8 Color Fastness to Wash Result

Table 11: Assessment of Color Fastness to Wash

Sample	Shade%	Di acetate	Cotton	Nylon	Polyester	Acrylic	Wool
Bio-scoured fabrics	1.0%	4/5	4	4/5	4/5	4/5	4/5
	2.0%	4/5	4/5	4/5	4/5	5	5
Caustic scoured fabrics	1.0%	4/5	3/4	4/5	4/5	4/5	4/5
	2.0%	4/5	4/5	4	4/5	4/5	4/5

Observation: Color fastness to wash demonstrates the effects in terms of color staining. These findings indicate that the wash materials vary in the caustic soda scoured specimen and the enzymatic scoured specimen depending on the nature of the color's fastness. Conventional scoured samples with reactive dye show a little bit different as opposed to the bio-scoured samples with reactive dye.

4.9 Water Consumption

Table 12: The Volume of Water Needed for the Processing of 10 Kg of Cloth at a Liquor Ratio of 1:8

Method	Liters
Conventional Scouring (appx)	428
Enzymatic Scouring (appx)	134

Observation: Since a wide range of chemical compounds were used to complete the cycle in conventional scouring; hence, a large amount of water was required for rinsing. On the contrary, we employ the enzyme rather than chemical substances in the scouring method; thus, less water was needed in this method. The quantity of water to be saved is approximately 29 liters per kilogram

treated. With a division making 25 Metric tons of scouring daily, the volume of water to be recovered is 725,000 liters each day. On a yearly basis, there are 264625.000 liters of water.

4.10 Time Consumption

Table 13: Assessment of Time Consumption

Method	Time
Conventional Scouring (appx)	2 hr. 50 min
Enzymatic Scouring (appx)	1 hr. 10 min

Observation: Caustic soda scouring takes a huge time compared to the enzymatic scouring method to complete the entire scouring method. Hence, it obviously saves a massive amount of time if we consider the enzymatic scouring method rather than the conventional scouring method.

4.11 Electricity and Stream Consumption

Table 14: Assessment of Electricity and Stream Consumption

Method	kWh	kg/kg of fabric
Conventional Scouring (appx)	22.34	1.8
Enzymatic Scouring (appx)	9.20	0.7

Observation: A huge amount of time was needed to execute the caustic method; as a result, the caustic scouring method consumed more electricity than the enzymatic scouring method. The quantity of electricity to be saved is more than half for bio-scouring. On the other hand, the amount of stream required for caustic scouring is considerably higher compared with enzymatic scouring. So, more than three-fifths stream has been saved in the enzymatic scouring.

4.12 Temperature Saving

Table 15: Assessment of Temp. Saving

Method	°C
Conventional Scouring	95
Enzymatic Scouring	55

Observation: The difference in temperature is about 40 ° C. Considering 1:8 materials to liquor ratio for one kilogram of cotton treated, 8 liters of water are needed throughout the scouring method.

The quantity of heat energy necessary per kilogram of cotton processed = $(95 - 55) \times 1000 \times 4.186 \times 8$
 = 1339520 Joules = 1339.52 kilojoules.

Where, water specific heat capacity 4186 Joule/gram K. To heat 1 gram of water by 1 Kelvin, 4.186 joules of energy are required.

The quantity of heat energy to be recovered is approximately 1339.52 kilojoules per kilogram material processed. With a division making 25 Metric tons of scouring daily, the volume of heat energy to be saved is 1.22 x10¹⁰ KJ each year.

4.13 Cost Analysis

4.13.1 Water Cost

Table 16: Water Cost for 1000 Kilograms Fabrics

Method	Litres	Cost (BDT)
Conventional Scouring (appx)	42800	313.724
Enzymatic Scouring (appx)	13400	98.222
Cost of water = BDT. 7.33/ 1000 liters		

4.13.2 Electricity Cost

Table 17: Assessment of Electricity Cost

Method	kWh	Cost (BDT)
Conventional Scouring (appx)	22.34	159.284
Enzymatic Scouring (appx)	9.20	65.596
Cost of electricity = BDT. 7.13/ kWh		

4.13.3 Stream Cost

Table 18: Assessment of Stream Cost for 1000 Kilograms Fabrics

Method	kg	Cost (BDT)
Conventional Scouring(appx)	1800	2304
Enzymatic Scouring (appx)	700	896
Cost of stream = BDT. 1.28/ kg		

4.13.4 Chemical Cost of enzyme scouring

Table 19: Chemical Cost for Bio-Scoured Fabrics

Chemicals	g/L	Unit Price (BDT)	Qty/ 1000 kg of fabric	Cost/ 1000 kg of fabric (BDT)
Bio-scouring enzyme	0.80%	595.80	0.064	38.13
Citric acid	0.20%	88.74	0.016	1.42
Wetting agent	1	375.0	8	3000
Anti-foaming agent	0.05	254.71	0.4	101.88
Detergent	1	465.0	8	3720
Total				6861.43

4.13.5 Chemical Cost of caustic scouring

Table 20: Assessment of Chemical Cost for Caustic Scoured Fabrics

Chemicals	g/L	Unit Price (BDT)	Qty/ 1000 kg of fabric	Cost/ 1000 kg of fabric (BDT)
Caustic soda	1	57	8	456
Soda ash	2	25.76	16	412.16
Wetting agent	1	375.0	8	3000
Anti-foaming agent	0.05	254.71	0.4	101.88
Detergent	2	465.0	16	7440
Citric acid	1.50	88.74	12	1064.88
Sequestering agent	0.20	110.0	1.6	176
Anti creasing agent	1	78.4	8	627.2
Total Cost				13278.12

Observation: Tables 15, 16, 17, 18 and 19 show that in traditional processes, the entire scouring price includes chemicals, steam, water, and electricity falls about BDT. 16055.13, while the cost of bio-scouring is BDT. 7921.25.

4.13.6 Effluent Treatment Cost

Table 21: Test Result of Wastewater Treatment Cost for 1000 Kilograms Fabrics

Method	Liters	Treatment Cost (BDT)
Conventional Scouring	42800	1098.3764
Enzymatic Scouring	13400	343.8842
Cost for one liter effluent = 0.025663BDT. Or, Cost for one cubic meter effluent = 25.66 BDT.		

Observation: The effluent produced by the traditional process is 42800 liters per 1,000 kg of fabrics, while the enzymatic method is 13400 liters. This results in an effluent load savings of 68.7% in bio-scouring. The cost of treatment of effluent is estimated to be BDT. 1098.3764 in the case of caustic scouring and BDT. 343.8842 in the case of enzymatic scouring, resulting in net savings of 68.7 % in the cost of bio-scouring treatment of effluent.

4.14 Physicochemical parameters Test Result

Table 22: Test Results of Physicochemical Parameters of Wastewater for Different Scouring Process

Sample No.	Material of effluents	Parameters	Units	Results			Department of Environment Standards for waste from industrial units
				N ¹	Mean	SD ²	
Sample No. 1 (Effluent from conventional scouring)	Detergent, Wetting agent, Caustic soda, soda ash, Cotton waste, citric acid, Sequestering agent, anti foaming agent, anti creasing agent	Biochemical Oxygen Demand	ppm	3	1812.33	12.81	50
		Chemical Oxygen Demand	ppm	3	3229	29.81	200
		Dissolved Oxygen	ppm	3	1.13	0.02	6
		Electrical Conductivity	mS/cm	3	28.51	0.07	12
		Total Solids	ppm	3	14533	28.58	–
		Total Suspended Solids	ppm	3	267	10.2	150
		Total Dissolved Solids	ppm	3	14266	26.09	2100
		Alkalinity	ppm	3	939.67	7.59	500
		pH	–	3	11.82	0.22	6–9
Sample No. 2 (Effluent from bio-scouring)	BioPrep® Fusion (bio-scouring enzyme), Wetting agent, Detergent	Biochemical Oxygen Demand	ppm	3	1003.7	3.3	50
		Chemical Oxygen Demand	ppm	3	2225	19.65	200
		Dissolved Oxygen	ppm	3	2.77	0.01	6
		Electrical Conductivity	mS/cm	3	6.29	0.02	12
		Total Solids	ppm	3	3316	25.96	–
		Total Suspended Solids	ppm	3	160	2.94	150
		Total Dissolved Solids	ppm	3	3156	23.04	2100
		Alkalinity	ppm	3	707	5.35	500
		pH	–	3	6.45	0.08	6–9

¹ Number of observations, and ² Standard Deviation

Observation: The study's outcome shows that the enzymatic scouring process has a greater ecological impact on the environment than alkaline scouring process. This is because the microorganism present here, i.e., the bio-scoring enzyme, is used as scouring agents. On the other hand, a lot of harsh chemical compounds are used in the alkaline scouring method. That is why BOD and COD values are considerably higher compared to enzymatic process.

Chapter Five

Conclusion

5.1 Overall Comparisons

Although comparison is the main topic of our research, our main target was to find out the usability and replace ability of bio-scouring process over conventional scouring processes. Thus we have tried to distinguish the advantages and the positive sides of bio - scouring. The prospect of bio – scouring can be assumed from the discussion below:

Fabric Strength: Fabric losses its strength significantly in traditional scouring than bio-scouring because of the nature of chemicals used in traditional scouring are harsher than bio-scoured chemicals. It is also because of bio-scouring agents attacking the primary cell wall of the fibers which is required for dye absorption, but conventional scouring agents attack both primary and secondary cell walls and cause greater strength loss.

Whiteness: Conventional scouring produces whiter fabric than bio-scouring produces. Thus, conventional scouring is more effective in manufacturing white-colored shades fabric, but to produce dark-colored shade fabrics bio-scouring gives the same result. If bleaching is followed by bio-scouring, then white fabric can be produced.

Weight Loss: Due to attacking also the secondary cell wall and high removal of pectin, although removal of pectin is not important for improving hydrophilicity or absorbency, fabric weight loss (about 3-10%) is higher. For these lost fabrics, the manufacturer has to pay extra cost.

Dye Loss: Higher removal of pectin causes higher space in the fibers for dyestuff penetration, reaction and fixation. Hence, conventional scoured fabrics dyeing needs higher amount of dyestuffs than dyeing of bio-scouring fabrics need.

Energy and Time Required: Bio-scouring needs not as high temperature as conventional scouring needs. Bio – scouring is done below 60°C, but conventional caustic scouring is done around 90°C-105°C temperature and to provide this higher temperature, higher heat production is needed. Therefore, high heat energy production increases cost in scouring. Moreover, after conventional scouring, two step washing is required for neutralizing high alkalinity. Which also increases additional time and cost.

Effluent Concern: A lot of harsh chemicals are used in conventional scouring process which is very much responsible to increase the amount of BOD, COD, DO (Dissolved Oxygen) and TDS (Total Dissolved Solids) in the effluent water and increase the unwanted pressure on

environment. Caustic scouring is responsible for the lion parts of the total effluent of a factory. 10-20% of the total pollution load generated during entire textile processing operation.

Color Fastness: Color fastness of the dyed fabrics after bio – scouring and conventional has nearly same though it varies from types of dyestuff, dyeing process, depth of shade, finishing process and other factors. Risk in handling: The handling of harsh chemicals increases the possibilities of accident. It may affect on workers health. In addition, some health-hazard chemicals may stay in the fabrics even after finishing processes which can affect on human health.

5.2 Conclusion

Although the traditional caustic cotton scouring method is being widely used these days, it is facing a quantity of water, power, stream, and time consumption, and higher fiber damage. Hence, sustainable, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly manufacturing are imperative in order to maintain environmental integrity, preserve energy, environmental assets, and minimize costs and effluents. As long as many dyeing plants are still using conventional caustic cotton pretreatment, they are consuming a large amount of energy, water, fiber loss, dye loss and color strength as well as are contributing towards environmental degradation. By executing empirical analysis, we arrived at the conclusion that the use of bio-scouring against traditional caustic cotton scouring facilitates the movement towards the development of environmentally friendly, cost-effective, and sustainable products. Enzyme scouring allows minimal ecological effect as opposed to conventional caustic cotton pretreatment. Because of the enzymatic scouring minimizes about 25% BOD and 43% COD in comparison to caustic scouring. As opposed to the caustic cotton pretreatment, bio-scouring reduces more than two-thirds of water, nearly three-fifths of time and electricity, just over three-fifths of the stream. In addition, enzyme scouring decreases just under half of the chemical cost, just above three-fifths of stream cost, more than half of electricity cost, just over two-thirds of ETP cost and water cost than traditional pretreatment. Also, bio-scouring loses a tiny fraction of fiber strength compared with the grey fabric. The chosen physical characteristics test reveals better result for enzyme scoured fabrics than caustic scoured cotton knit fabrics. Although enzyme scouring process is not at all a solution for all types of shade due to value of whiteness index, enzyme scouring process is being used for dark shade till now as it can capture an excellent outcome for dark shade, but light, medium and white shade cannot be achieved by enzyme scouring process; thus, a solution for these shade could be developed in the near future. This work represents a small obtainment to better reliable activists which would lead to the

implementation of various sustainability questions for textile and apparel manufacturers, producers, distributors, clients and consumers. Thus, to bring consciousness and take them on sustainable activities for the textile mills in order to make the world healthier and greener. Everyone who participates in a textile production process must be respectful to the environment and maintain the image of our clothing in developed countries for the betterment of our nations.

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